

Voltammetric studies of furfural and its trace determination

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A detailed electrochemical studies on furfural at mercury electrode has been reported. A linear sweep voltammetric method has been developed for low level determination of furfural and other aliphatic aldehydes simultaneously. This method has been used for the determination of acetaldehyde and furfural in liquor samples. The detection limit ranged between 0.05–1.0 ppm for different aldehydes.

Furfural, an aldehydic derivative of furan, is a common flavouring agent in a variety of food products and beverages. Furfural is discharged in waste water and waste gases from yeast production and other industrial effluents. It is considered an atmospheric pollutant and has been found to induce allergy, asthma and cirrhosis¹. Potential genotoxicity of furfural has been discussed in detail², wherein LD50 in mice and rabbit has been reported to be in 200–300 mg kg⁻¹. Presence of furfural and aliphatic aldehydes in spirit liquors in sufficient quantities enhance the paralyzing effect of alcohol on nervous system. Aldehydes are secondary constituents of spirit liquors and furfural is formed during distillation. According to the Indian Standard code³ the permissible limit for total aldehyde in rum is 600 ppm and furfural should be absent. Several reports are there on low level determination of furfural by spectrophotometry⁴, fluorimetry⁵, HPLC⁶ and gas chromatography⁷ in a variety of sample matrices. However, voltammetry is a relatively simple instrumental technique which has the potential for qualitative and quantitative analysis for a number of carbonyl compounds at trace levels^{8–10}. Semicarbazone derivative of furfural has also been found reducible at the dropping mercury electrode¹¹. It appeared from literature survey that a systematic investigation on electrochemical behaviour of furfural using advanced voltammetric techniques has not been done. Therefore, the present investigation was undertaken to study the electrochemical reduction behaviour of furfural in detail, using DC, DPP, CV and LSV techniques at mercury electrode. A linear sweep voltammetric (LSV) method has also been suggested for low level estimation of furfural and aliphatic aldehydes simultaneously. The proposed voltammetric method has been applied to different liquor samples, to estimate the acetaldehyde and furfural content.

Results and discussion

DC polarogram of furfural revealed a well-defined single wave in different supporting electrolytes viz., 0.1 M LiOH, 0.1 M LiCl and B.R. buffer (pH 2 to 11.8) at dropping mercury electrode. The limiting currents were linear function of concentration and $h^{1/2}$ (h = height of mercury column), indicating their diffusion controlled nature. The differential pulse polarogram (DPP) corresponded well with DC polarogram (Fig. 1) and their peak currents were also linear function of concentration. This signal is attributed to the reduction of aldehyde to corresponding alcohol consuming two electrons, as evident from current function calculation from DC polarographic data.

The cyclic voltammogram (HMDE) at pH 2, 4, 7, 9, 11.8 (Fig. 2) and in alkaline supporting electrolyte revealed a cathodic peak in the forward negative scan in the potential range -0.7 to -1.7 V vs Ag/AgCl and no anodic peak in the reverse scan, indicating irreversibility of the electrode process. Cathodic peak potential (E_{pc}) shifted to negative values with increasing scan rate, also establish the irreversibility. Cathodic peak current (i_{pc}) was proportional to concentration and to $v^{1/2}$ (v = scan rate), again signifying diffusion controlled nature of the electrode process. The transfer coefficient, $\alpha.n_a$ values calculated from $E_p - E_{p/2} = 47.7/\alpha.n_a$, mV relationship and the diffusion coefficient (D) values were calculated from relationship $i_p = (2.99 \times 10^5) n (\alpha.n_a)^{1/2} A.C.D.^{1/2}.v^{1/2}$ for totally irreversible charge transfer process¹². Table I includes cyclic voltammetric characteristics and kinetic parameters of electrochemical reduction of furfural.

Linear sweep voltammogram were utilized for analytical purpose. For quantitation purpose 0.1 M LiOH has been proposed as supporting electrolyte for two reasons, firstly sharp peaks and secondly simultaneous determination of

Fig. 1. Polarograms of 5 mM furfural in 0.1 M LiOH at dme (scan rate 5 mV s⁻¹).

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammograms of 0.5 mM furfural at HMDE at pH 2 (a), 4 (b), 6 (c), 8 (d), 9 (e) and 11.8 (f), scan rate 5 mV s⁻¹.

other aldehydes was possible due to extended negative potential range. Quantitation was achieved by standard addition method. The limit of detection (LOD) was found to be 0.5 ppm which gave a peak of height 3 mm at current sensitivity 0.002 mA V⁻¹ at scan rate 100 mV s⁻¹.

To evaluate the accuracy of a voltammetric method, a known volume of pure ethanol was spiked with standard stock solution of furfural. Voltammograms of these synthetic samples were recorded and the results included in Table 2 show a fairly good precision and reproducibility of the method.

Table 1. Cyclic voltammetric characteristics of 0.5 mM furfural at HMDE (scan rate 60 mV s⁻¹)

Supporting electrolyte	E_{pc} V	i_{pc} μA	$E_{pc}-E_{pc/2}$ mV	$\alpha.n_a$	$D \times 10^6$ cm ² s ⁻¹
B.R. Buffer pH 2.0	-1.000	0.570	50	0.95	0.8
pH 4.0	-1.160	0.725	60	0.89	1.3
pH 6.0	-1.260	0.750	60	0.89	1.4
pH 7.0	-1.315	0.775	60	0.89	1.5
pH 8.0	-1.375	0.925	60	0.89	2.1
pH 9.0	-1.410	1.075	60	0.89	2.8
pH 11.0	-1.415	1.225	50	0.97	3.7
pH 11.8	-1.405	1.275	55	0.93	4.0
0.1 M LiCl	-1.410	1.100	40	1.09	2.9
0.1 M LiOH	-1.400	1.220	40	1.09	3.6
Mean				0.917	

Table 2. Recovery of added furfural in the synthetic samples*

Conc. added ppm	Conc. recovered ppm	RSD %
5	4.99	2.58
10	10.07	1.88
15	15.00	1.83
20	19.89	2.72

*Average of three determination.

The interferences due to acetone and acetic acid were checked. Presence of acetone up to 0.07 M had no effect on the voltammogram of furfural (0.01 mM), however above this concentration an additional peak start appearing at about 150 mV more positive to reduction peak of furfural. Presence of acetic acid up to 0.1 M does not have any effect on voltammogram of furfural (0.1 mM); however at higher concentration, peak current decreases, peak shift to more positive potential and working potential range gets shortened due to decreasing pH of solution.

In LiOH medium, it was possible to obtain a sharp reduction peak of formaldehyde and acetaldehyde/propionaldehyde/butyraldehyde along with that of the furfural at HMDE. Voltammetric reduction peak potential and their LOD under proposed conditions are included in Table 3.

Determination of furfural in liquor samples :

The liquor samples obtained from Central Excise Department, Jodhpur, were analyzed by voltammetry for determination of furfural and acetaldehyde content. To the 5 ml of 0.2 M LiOH, 5 ml of samples were added and voltammograms were recorded as described earlier. Furfural was found to be nil in all the samples, however a sharp

Table 3. Voltammetric signal of various aldehydes at HMDE

Analyte	Furfural	Formaldehyde	Acetaldehyde	Propionaldehyde	Butyraldehyde
Supporting electrolyte = 0.1 M LiOH, scan rate = 50 mV s ⁻¹					
E_p , volt	-1.41	-1.74	-1.95	-1.88	-1.69
LOD, ppm	0.5	1.0	0.6	0.1	0.05

peak was obtained at -1.95 V vs Ag/AgCl, corresponding to acetaldehyde reduction peak, which was confirmed by standard method (Fig. 3). Analysis of Indian Rum and Whisky sample are included in Table 4. Results obtained were in agreement with those obtained by iodometric method⁴.

It can be concluded that linear sweep voltammetry offers sufficient accuracy and practicability for rapid monitoring of furfural at low concentration levels.

Fig. 3. Voltammograms for the simultaneous determination of mixture of aldehydes in a liquor sample in 0.1 M LiOH at HMDE (at 60 mV s⁻¹): (i) liquor sample, (ii) standard addition of 40 ppm each of furfural (a), formaldehyde (b) and acetaldehyde (c).

Experimental

A PAR 174 A Polarographic analyzer with a droptimer (174/70) and X-V recorder (REO074) was used for DC and differential pulse polarographic (DPP) experiments. The dropping mercury electrode (DME) had following characteristics: $m = 0.233 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$ and $t = 3 \text{ s}$; for DPP experiments modulation amplitude 50 mV and clock time of pulse as 1s was used. The potential were measured against saturated calomel electrode (SCE) in DC and DPP experiments. Cyclic voltammetry (CV) and linear sweep voltammetry

Table 4. Analysis of liquor samples at HMDE

Liquor sample (n = 10)	Furfural (ppm)	Acetaldehyde		
		Min.	Max.	Average*
Whisky	Nil	29.8	34.4	31.5
Rum	Nil	86.4	94.5	90.5

*Average of 10 determinants each in duplicate.

(LSV) were performed on a BAS CV-27 cyclic voltammograph. A Metrohm, hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE, area $1.82 \times 10^{-2} \text{ cm}^2$) as working electrode and silver-silver chloride electrode (Ag/AgCl) as reference electrode were used in CV and LSV experiments. A platinum wire was used as an auxiliary electrode throughout. Triple-distilled mercury was used for working electrode. All experiments were carried out in an air conditioned laboratory maintained at 25°. All chemicals used were of A.R. grade and aliphatic aldehyde from Merck-Schuchardt were used as received. Furfural was distilled under reduced pressure before use. Solution containing supporting electrolyte (0.1 M) was de-aerated by passing N₂ gas for 15 min, however after adding aldehyde/sample the de-aeration was carried out for a further 30 s only. A 50 mM stock solution of aldehydes (furfural, formaldehyde, acetaldehyde, propionaldehyde and butyraldehyde) were prepared in ethanol and further dilution was done with supporting electrolyte.

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